

A GIRL'S BRA – A GIRL'S PRIDE

Akina, Sau-han Chow – Institute of Textiles and Clothing, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hung Hom, Hong Kong, (852) 60809051, akinachow@hotmail.com

Wenling Xiao – Institute of Textile and Fashion Arts, Tsinghua University, Beijing, China (086)-1062798876, xiaowenling@163.com

Wing-sun Liu – Institute of Textiles and Clothing, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hung Hom, Hong Kong, (852)27666444, tcliuws@polyu.edu.hk

Abstract

Central to the idea of postmodernism is the notion that people are consuming images (Baudrillard, 1998; Debord, 1977) in the market in the crafting of selves (Kondo, 1990; Thompson, 1990). It is envisioned that the sense of fragmented selves (Gergen, 1991) as characterized in the postmodern context is even more acute among youngsters. Of all of the items in a girl's wardrobe, nothing is more important to her identity than her bras. This is a quasi-ethnographic (Fetterman, 1998; Hammersley and Atkinson, 1997) study to explore the symbolic meanings of bras among female adolescents in Hong Kong. There is a strong maternal influence in the very context of the bra; at the same time, the color black for a bra carries a strong connotation of sexiness. This item is full of visually implicit meanings, which are probably explicit to a girl as she is growing up.

Conference theme: Desire and Lust

Keywords: bras, identity, post-modernism

Introduction

Central to the idea of postmodernism is the notion that people are consuming images (Baudrillard, 1998; Debord, 1977) in the market in the crafting of selves (Kondo, 1990; Thompson, 1990). It is envisioned that the sense of fragmented selves (Gergen, 1991) as characterized in the postmodern context is even more acute among adolescents. Of all of the items in a girl's wardrobe, nothing is more important to her identity than her bras. This item, however, is full of visually implicit meanings that are probably explicit to a girl as she is growing up.

A lack of research in Asian countries such as China concerning consumer behavior in purchasing bras may be a result of the taboo in Chinese society on discussing sex and intimacy. According to a report released by the group Women of China (2006), China's underwear market is predicted to grow 20 percent annually in the next ten years. Thus, the value of a study on the consumption behavior of females with regard to bras is significant.

Literature

Consumption in Postmodernity

By the late twentieth century, consumption to fulfill symbolic needs of people, outweighed that for practical and utilitarian needs (McCracken, 1986). People in postmodern society are threatened by a number of "dilemmas of the self" (Giddens, 1991, 201), for instance, fragmentation, powerlessness, uncertainty and a struggle against commodification. These dilemmas are driven by the "looming threat of a person's meaninglessness" as the individual endeavors to construct and maintain an identity so as to remain stable through a dramatically changing environment. Everyone is striving for an ideal "packaged lifestyle" (Giddens, 1991). People emphasize surface appearance and extrinsic presentations (Lury, 1996, 77-78); "conspicuous consumption" is the result.

People tend to reflect and express their self-identity by consuming intangible symbolic meanings in postmodern world instead of consuming the utilitarian attributes of goods. "Living in a symbol-rich environment, consumers use symbolic meanings to construct, maintain and express their multiple identities" (Elliott and Wattanasuwan, 1998).

The symbolic meanings of products function on two levels: "external in constructing the social world, social-symbolism, and internal in constructing our self-identity, self-symbolism" (Elliott,

1997). Advertising is recognized as one of the most potent sources of the symbolic meanings generated from consumption. During the process of constructing and maintaining an individual's identity, brands are frequently used as symbolic resources (Mick and Buhl, 1992).

Girls' Identity and Bras

As stated by Kroger (2005), although the foundations of gender identity are developed in early childhood, the task of clearly defining oneself as male or female and integrating one's emerging sexual identity with one's sense of personal identity is an important task of mid-adolescence. Furthermore, Gilligan (1982) indicated that girls put much effort on their appearance and on personal maintenance than boys, by using cosmetics, hairstyles and clothing in order to project a heterosexually desirable gender identity.

For girls, adolescence is a difficult and vulnerable time when they focus attention on their bodies (Koff, 1983), in a culture such as Hong Kong that demands perfect female bodies (Brownmiller, 1984).

As defined by Morris (2004), the two biological functions of breasts are "parental" and "sexual." She concluded that the hemispherical shape of the breasts is not a parental development. She stated that "the response of males to the prominent breasts of a virgin or non-lactating female is a reaction to a primeval sex signal of the human species."

The newfangled brassiere had two quite distinct functions. It protected large breasts, preventing them from bouncing awkwardly during rapid body movements, and it also made them look firm and round, and therefore sexier (Morris, 2004).

Reference Groups

From a consumer-behavior perspective, it appears that the products and brands that individuals select can be influenced by their reference groups (Bearden and Etzel, 1982). Kelley (1947) has refined and clarified two types of reference groups: "comparative reference groups," which are used for self-appraisal; and "normative reference groups", which are groups that are used as a source of personal norms, attitudes, and values.

In extended families, the influence of family members on the consumption behavior of individuals is likely to be relatively strong. Childers and Rao (1992) focused on the intergenerational transfer of brand loyalties as one key measure of intergenerational influence.

Specifically, they predicted that offspring would be more likely to purchase the same brand as their parents for privately versus publicly consumed products.

Quasi-ethnography

Market-oriented ethnographies aim at adding to the knowledge of what human behaviors and experiences are in reality (Wells, 1993), through “thick descriptions” (Geertz, 1973) of the social and cultural meanings behind such behaviors and experiences.

It was difficult to carry out a true ethnographic study due to the constraints of time, budget, and experience. Consequently, the decision was made to conduct a quasi-ethnographic study instead, employing several techniques approximating those used in ethnography.

Ten key informants were recruited: five secondary school students and five undergraduate students, all aged from 16 to 21. Moreover, the author would chat with friends, students, and relatives whenever possible, so as to collect triangular data from general perceptions on the topic.

The two main ethnographic techniques were employed for collecting primary data: in-depth interviews and informal interviews and casual conversations. Secondary data such as newspapers and academic journals were also examined to for insights, stimuli and background on the latest trends in the country.

1. Clara (16) S.5 Student	Middle-income family, pretty and chic, dancer, volleyball player, her elder sister is a professional dancer
2. Michelle (16) S.5 Student	Middle-income family, born in South Africa, outgoing and tough, basketball player
3. Renee (16) S.4 Student	Middle-income family, close relationship with her younger brother
4. Kelly (17) S.6 Student	Middle-income family, has an aunt who always goes shopping with her, loyal to brands
5. K (16) S.4 Student	Middle-income family, has an elder sister who always goes shopping with her, charming and fascinating, volleyball

	player
6. Sue (19) Year 1 Student	Lower-income family, shy girl, Christian, has a younger sister, delicate
7. Venus (21) Year 1 Student	Low-income family, came to Hong Kong at 11 years old, has two younger sisters, works part-time in a cinema, optimistic and energetic
8. Lee (21) Year 2 Student	Lower-middle income family, devoted Christian family, an only daughter, gentle and cultivated
9. Amy (20) Year 1 Student	Lower-middle income family, Christian, has a younger sister, gentle and polite
10. Kitty (20) Year 2 Student	Lower-middle income family, Christian, talkative, outstanding in drama

Table 1: Profile of the Informants

Findings and Discussion

There are various factors contributing to the consumption behavior of girls purchasing bras. It was discovered in the study that the most potent factor is “maternal influence. The change in the identity of girls was revealed from a shift in their behavior, “from rejecting the bra to pursuing the bra.” Furthermore, the perception that “black bras are sexy” and the underlying reasons for this will be explored. The reason why girls look for beautiful bras and their intention to purchase bras by themselves, not in the company of others, will be discussed as well.

Maternal Influence in a different context

Childers and Rao (1992) found that the intergenerational influence on the purchasing of private necessities was greater in extended families than in nuclear families. All of the girls in this study came from extended families in Hong Kong with kinship-based cultures. The maternal influence on the consumption of bras is profound in various aspects: their first bra, brands, styles and quality, and laundry and storage.

First bra

The purchase of their first bra is an exciting and mysterious experience for girls. Although their experiences differ, one similarity is the fact that their mother accompanied them on the trip, or

even purchased the bra for them without telling them first. It is common for mothers to choose a flesh-colored bra for their daughters' first bra. White is another common choice of mothers. The color and style of a girl's first bra tends to be plain and simple.

The experience of Kelly (17) is an extreme example of the latter case. Without prior notice, her mother brought Kelly her first bra. Kelly has never even been to a bra shop. She accepts the current situation, although she wonders whether her bras are really the right size for her.

Before the purchase

Most of the girls were nervous before the purchase of their first bra. Some of them looked forward to having their first bra, while a few of them refused to buy their first bra.

Clara (16): "I felt nervous because I didn't know what to buy and I was afraid that I would buy something I disliked. I expected to have a pretty bra so I was excited."

In some cases, the reaction of girls was strong, since they disliked or even felt disgusted about the idea of wearing a bra.

Renee (16): "When my mother told me that I would have to wear bra, I was afraid. I disliked the idea of wearing bra because I felt that it would be uncomfortable to be bound by a bra."

During the purchase

Mothers played the main role during the purchase of a girl's first bra. Kelly's case was extreme in that she did not participate in any way in the purchasing process. The mother of this 17 year-old girl still buys her bras for her.

Venus (21): "During the whole process, I did not say anything and I did not have a chance to choose or express opinions."

The girls were very passive when choosing their first bra. They were excited and had great expectations regarding their first bra. However, they tended to not express these ideas and feelings.

After the purchase

Most of the girls changed their impression about wearing bras after they owned their first bra. The nervousness and excitement that they had initially felt disappeared in their second trip to purchase bras. However, even if some girls felt that the bras that they were wearing were the wrong size for them, they would not say anything to their mothers. This shows how difficult it is for girls to express themselves on sex-related topics in a Chinese society.

Brands

One key intergenerational influence is the intergenerational transfer of brand loyalties (Woodson, Childers, and Winn, 1976). Most of the girls consume the same brand of bra as their mothers, especially in the case of their first bra.

Renee (16): “Sometimes I may buy Calvin Klein Underwear, as I think the style is more fashionable. But we usually go to Triumph, since my mother loyal to this brand. I like Triumph as well, since their bras are comfortable.”

Figure 1: Renee’s Calvin Klein and Triumph bras

Styles and quality

With regard to bra styles, the girls’ preferences were also influenced by their mothers. The girls’ perceptions of what constitutes good quality in bras and which styles benefit the development of breasts was formed from their mothers’ teaching. Some girls chose bras similar to those that their mothers preferred, even after they became financially independent.

Laundering and storage

They were told the appropriate laundering and storage methods by the sales girls. Nevertheless, most of the girls followed the same laundering and storage methods as the ones their mothers used. This is in accord with the observation of Elliott et al. (1993) that: “Signification through the media is likely to be much less potent than signification through actual behavioral experience.”

Kitty (21): “The sales girl reminded me to wash it by hand, but I did not do so. I followed the laundering method of my mother.”

Exceptional cases in low-income families

There were two girls who did not consume the same brand as their mothers: Sue and Venus. Both come from low-income families and, from early adolescence, have had to purchase the types of bras that they favor with their own savings. With them, the maternal influence on brands and styles was less potent.

Sue (19): “I disliked those styles purchased by my mother as they were out-dated. Therefore, I went to Triumph with my classmates to buy my first bra that I liked.”

Venus (21): “I hated that flesh-colored bra brought by my mother. I told my mother that the bra was unfit for me and well worn. Then, I went to Wacoal with my friends to purchase a bra using my pocket money.”

Identity Ambivalence

Gordan and Lahelma (2004) claimed that many young women want to accelerate their shift towards independent adult status. At the same time, some of them try to postpone the moment when they will be locked into the lives of adult women.

From rejecting bras to pursuing bras

Some of the girls refused to wear a bra and, when they were younger, did not want to have a bosomy figure. However, they gradually perceived the importance of their developing breasts and began wearing bras spontaneously as they grew up. This turnaround during the period of adolescence in their perceptions of breasts and bras and their pursuit of a perfect figure reflects their desire and emerging sense of becoming an adult female.

KaKa (16): “I felt disgusted and I assumed that wearing a bra is inconvenient and troublesome. I also felt that having big breasts is not good and that they are unattractive, because my classmates always teased me. I remember telling my mother that I do not want to have big breasts. But now, I am quite satisfied with the size of my breasts. I have more confidence about my breasts.”

Obviously, besides protecting the breasts, another important function of the bra is to improve the shape of a woman’s breasts. Girls were attracted by bras and began to look for a suitable bra because of the latter function of the bra. The importance of body image and the pursuit of a perfect figure imply the desire of a girl to express her gender identity. A bra that accentuates the shape of the breasts becomes an identity symbol of being a woman. This is an example of the claim of Elliott and Wattanasuwan (1998) that people are consuming the symbolic meanings, thus bras for girls, so as to reflect and express their self-identity.

Private versus Public

Markus and Kitayama (1991) illustrated the idea of the “awareness of others’ perceptions” of oneself in their discussion on the private self and public self. This “awareness” is significant in this study.

Bras are private

Some girls prohibited the interviewer from taking photos of their bras. They felt that bras are their intimate and personal belongings, and thus do not want to expose them to others. Clara (16) refused to allow photos of her bras to be taken, but allowed the interviewer to visit her sister’s room and take photos of her sister’s fancy bras. Her sister is a dancer who has excessive clothing, including bras.

Figure 2: The fancy bras of Clara's sister

Beautiful bras for self-appreciation

Many would say that women's underwear, in particular, is worn for the pleasure and privilege of the male gaze. Most of the girls in this study were single. It was assumed that their intention in purchasing bras was not to please men. However, the girls were still consumers of pretty bras.

Lee (21): "I like beautiful bras. I can appreciate my own body. If I wear a pretty and fitted bra, I feel comfortable and happier. I think all girls wish to possess beautiful things."

Girls tend to possess beautiful items for their "own narcissistic pleasure" and as a way of encouraging themselves. It has been shown in the study of Tse (1996) that Hong Kong students are receptive to consumption as a "life reward" and "a source of daily satisfaction."

Not to be interpreted?

In her study, Lee (1994) found that most women were more concerned and anxious about how their developing bodies looked and might be interpreted by others, than about how they looked or felt to themselves. The issue of breast development seemed to be a source of particular anxiety.

According to the informants, it was nothing out of the ordinary for girls to be teased and by boys in school about their breasts, and to hear crude comments about them, whether big or small. However, it was rare for girls to comment on small breasts among themselves, as they realized the depression that some girls felt after being teased about this by others.

KaKa (16): "My classmates had teased me to my face about my big breasts. We would not openly tease small-breasted girls because we were afraid making them depressed. But some naughty boys would tease them, ignoring their feelings."

Some girls with bigger breasts dislike push-up bras and feel a woman who wears such a bra is a fake.

Amy (21): “I have never worn a push-up bra, and I would never, ever, buy one. I feel it is fake, and a simple style is okay for me.”

Figure 4: Amy’s unpadded bra

On the contrary, girls with smaller breasts wished their breasts looked bigger; hence, push-up bras were their favorite choice of bra. Their underlying reason for using push-up bras to help them to present a better figure to others is the fear of being mocked.

Black bras are sexy

“Sexy, mysterious, womanly, smart, beautiful, chic, and wild” were words used by the girls to describe black bras.

KaKa (16): They are sexier. Black accentuates the shape of a bra. Black bras are more beautiful and I seem to become an adult when I wear one.”

Venus (21) looked forward to owning a black bra. She used the word “conservative” to describe her mother, who she thought would prohibit her from buying a black bra. It reflected an interesting impression of the girls that it is modish and fashionable to wear a black bra.

Venus (21): “I felt that classmates who wore black bras were chic and smart, and were not pure anymore. I was afraid that my mother would not allow me to buy a black bra because she is conservative. I felt I was different from others when I was wearing a black bra.”

Most of the girls would buy bras with removable straps and black bra straps, allowing them to change the straps of their bras to black straps, even if they are wearing bras of other colors. They want to find any opportunity of exposing black bra straps. Kelly (17), who has never purchased her own bras, asked her mother to buy her bras with removable straps, so that she would be able to change into black bra straps as well. She was hesitant about asking her mother to let her come along with her to buy her bras, but she bravely asked for black bra straps. This reflected the importance to her of possessing black bra straps.

Conclusion

In the above analysis, it could be concluded that maternal influence is the most prominent factor governing the consumption patterns and purchase decisions relating to bras among girls from middle-income families. This can be explained by the domination of “lived experiences” over “mediated experiences” (Elliott and Wattanasuwan, 1998).

However, the consumption patterns and purchase decisions of girls from low-income families are different from those from middle-income families. The maternal influence on them is less potent, since they became financially independent earlier; therefore, the influence on them from “mediated experience” is more significant.

The symbolic meaning of the bra to girls has been shown by the changes in identity that they experience as they transition from being girls to becoming adult women. A bra that accentuates the shape of their breasts is a symbol of women’s gender identity. Girls who pursue a perfect figure and wish to possess beautiful bras are exhibiting behavior that is a reaction to their innermost desire to express their gender identity. The culture in Hong Kong that demands a perfect female figure is another reason why girls focus their attention on their bodies.

The bra is a woman’s most intimate piece of apparel. It is assumed that females would have high requirements and demands of bras. However, girls tend to express their ideas and strive for independence in choosing clothing and accessories, but not bras. They prefer and seek beautiful bras because of a sense of gender identity. They do not realize how to define quality, and whether or not a bra is comfortable. To some extent, when they were young they assumed and perceived that bras were not comfortable. Therefore, comfort is not a critical concern for girls. Their lack of knowledge about the quality of bras means that they are dependent on their mothers and on sales personnel for their consumption of bras.

References

- Baudrillard, J. (1998). *The Consumer Society: Myths and Structures*. London: Sage Publications.
- Bearden, W. O. & Etzel, M. J. (1982). Reference Group Influence on Product and Brand Purchase Decisions. *The Journal of Consumer Research*, 9(2), pp. 183-194.
- Brownmiller, S. (1984). *Femininity*. New York: Ballantine.
- Childers, T. L. & Rao, A. R. (1992). The Influence of Familial and Peer-based Reference Groups on Consumer Decisions. *The Journal of Consumer Research*, 19(2), pp. 198-211.
- Debord, G. (1977). *Society of the Spectacle*. Detroit: Black and Red.
- Douglas, M. & Isherwood, B. (1978). *The World of Goods: Towards an Anthropology of Consumption*. New York: W. W. Norton.
- Elliott, R. (1997). Existential consumption and irrational desire. *European Journal of Marketing*, 31(34), pp. 285-296.
- Elliott, R., Eccles, S. & Hodgson, M. (1993). Re-coding gender representations: women, cleaning products, and advertising's "New Man". *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 10, pp. 311-324.
- Elliott, R. & Wattanasuwan K. (1998). Brands as symbolic resources for the construction of identity. *International Journal of Advertising*, 17(2), pp. 131-144.
- Fetterman, D. M. (1998). *Ethnography – Step by Step*. London: Sage.
- Geertz, C. (1973). *The Interpretation of Cultures*. New York: Basic Books.
- Gergen, K. (1991). *The Saturated Self: Dilemma of Identity in Contemporary Life*. New York: Basic Books.
- Giddens, A. (1991). *Modernity and Self-Identity: Self and Society in the Late Modern Age*. Cambridge: Polity Press.

Gilligan, C. (1982). *In a Different Voice: Psychological Theory and Women's Development*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.

Gordan, T. & Lahelma, E. (2004). Who wants to be a woman? Young women's reflections on transitions to adulthood. *Feminist Review*, 78, pp. 80-98.

Hammersley, M. and Atkinson P. (1997). *Ethnography – principles in practice*. London: Routledge.

Kelley, H. H. (1947). Two Functions of Reference Groups. In G. E. Swanson *et al.* (Ed.), *Readings in Social Psychology*, pp. 410-414. New York: Holt, Rinehart & Winston.

Koff, E. (1983). Through the looking glass of menarche: What the adolescent girl sees. In S. Goulib (Ed.), *Menarche: The transition from girl to woman*. Lexington, MA: D. C. Heath.

Kondo, D. K. (1990). *Crafting Selves*. London: The University of Chicago Press.

Kroger, J. (2005). *Identity development: adolescence through adulthood*. London: Sage Publications, Inc.

Lee, J. (1994). Menarche and the (hetero)sexualization of the female body. *Gender & Society*, 8(3), pp. 343-362.

Lury, C. (1996). *Consumer Culture*. Cambridge: Polity Press.

Markus, H. & Kitayama, S. (1991). Culture and Self-Implications for Cognition, Emotion and Motivation. *Psychological Review*, 98(2), pp. 224-253.

McCracken, G. (1986). Culture and Consumption: A Theoretical Account of the Structure and Movement of the Cultural Meanings of Consumer Goods. *Journal of Consumer Behavior*, 13, June, pp. 71-84.

Mick, D. G. & Buhl, C. (1992). A meaning-based model of advertising experiences. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 19, December, pp. 317-338.

Morris, D. (2004). *The Naked Woman – A study of the female body*. New York: St. Martin's Press.

Thompson, J. B. (1990). *Ideology and Modern Culture*. New York: Polity Press.

Tse, D. K. (1996). Understanding Chinese People as Consumers: Past Findings and Future Propositions. In M. H. Bond (Ed.), *The Handbook of Chinese Psychology*, pp. 352-363. New York: Oxford University Press.

Wells, W. (1993). Discovery-oriented Consumer Research. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 19, March, pp. 489-504.

Women of China. 13 April 2006. Study: Chinese Women Boast Improved Figure. Retrieved 01 March 2007 from <http://www.womenofchina.cn/news/society/3250.jsp>

Woodson, L. G., Childers, T. L. & Winn, P. R. (1976). Intergenerational Influences in the Purchase of Auto Insurance. In W. B. Locander (Ed.), *Marketing Looking Outward: 1976 Business Proceedings*, pp. 43-49. Chicago: American Marketing Association.